

Report from MISST

MULTI-SENSOR IMPROVED SST

MISST: Multi-sensor Improved SST-current

- In situ field campaign, joint with NOAA/PMEL:
 - 2019: 150-day Arctic cruise, 2 NASA + 3 NOAA Saildrones, data on GTS
 - Coordinated with Saildrone/PO.DAAC on file format.
 - NASA data at [PODAAC](#), NOAA data at [ERDDAP](#)
 - Submitted 2018 *in situ* data to felyx and ICOADS systems
- MODIS/VIIRS - Arctic uncertainty analysis, new cloud mask algorithm
- Implemented diurnal warming modeling for the Arctic region and initiated evaluation of predictions.
- OISST L4: OISST v2.1 new version was released! Mean bias reduced to -0.01C
- [MUR SST](#): AWS Public dataset program in Zarr format
- Analysis of L4 products in Arctic and SST/ice mask inconsistencies
- Terra and Aqua MODIS SST_{skin} reprocessing (R2019) has improved accuracy >60°N: cloud screening and optimized atmospheric correction.
- NAVOCEANO Metop-C SST with 4um cloud contamination test at low sun elevation (twilight)
- MODIS R2019 Aqua/Terra L2P datasets released to public
- Survey of GHRSSST data producer services and access capabilities conducted
- Five new SST datasets archived at LTSRF and LTSRF migrated to new NCEI location.

Registry of Open Data on AWS

Multi-Scale Ultra High Resolution (MUR) Sea Surface Temperature (SST)

[climate](#) [earth observation](#) [environmental](#) [natural resource](#) [oceans](#) [satellite imagery](#) [sustainability](#) [water](#)

Description

A global, gap-free, gridded, daily 1 km Sea Surface Temperature (SST) dataset created by merging multiple Level-2 satellite SST datasets. These input datasets include the NASA Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-EOS (AMSR-E), the JAXA Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer 2 (AMSR-2) on GCOM-W1, the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometers (MODIS) on the NASA Aqua and Terra platforms, the US Navy microwave WindSat radiometer, the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) on several NOAA satellites, and in situ SST observations from the NOAA Quam project. Data are available from 2002 to present in Zarr format. The original source of the MUR data is the NASA JPL Physical Oceanography DAAC.

Update Frequency

Daily

License

There are no restrictions on the use of these data.

Documentation

<https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/MUR-JPL-L4-GLOB-v4.1>

Managed By

<https://faralloninstitute.org>

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Contact

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Physical Oceanography Program

FARALLON INSTITUTE

MISST: Multi-sensor Improved SST-future

- In situ field campaigns:
 - 2021: 2 NASA Saildrones go to Arctic (will be submitted to PO.DAAC)
 - Data from 30+ more Saildrone cruises to submit to felyx/ICOADS systems
 - Analysis of diurnal warming and salinity fronts in Arctic
 - Assessment of spatial variability in the MIZ
 - Analysis of L4 uncertainties
- ICOADS new Daily version, merging TAC + BUFR data streams
- MUR SST - updates to production code, inclusion of day-time input data.
- Work with GHRSSST partners on Zarr-ification of data for cloud computing
- Analysis of L4 products in Arctic
- NAVOCEANO GAC L2P AVHRR (Metop-A,-B,-C), evaluate in the Arctic
- Outreach to Polar scientists to incorporate more in situ data into ICOADS
- Analysis of ice flagging in the Arctic, comparisons with ECCO2 Darwin model
- Work towards improved atmospheric correction algorithm for MODIS Arctic SST
- Work towards adding OSPO Metop-A/B/C SST to LTSRF archive and improving LTSRF.

